

Research article

From material synthesis to electrode processing, a holistic approach to enhance LiFePO₄ sustainability

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ABSTRACT

Lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO₄) is becoming the cathode of choice for Li-ion batteries due to its low cost, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced safety with long cycle life compared to layered oxides. In the present work, LiFePO₄ is synthesized via hydrothermal liquefaction and coated with a carbon layer derived from biomass waste to enhance sustainability. The performance of the resulting C-coated LiFePO₄ is evaluated and compared with LiFePO₄ coated with sucrose-derived carbon; both materials exhibit comparable electrochemical performance with respective discharge capacities of 96 and 93 mAh/g at 1 C with a capacity retention of 98 % and 96 %, respectively, after 100 cycles, demonstrating the viability of biomass-derived precursor for sample coating. Additionally, to improve the environmental friendliness of the electrode fabrication process while continuing with the holistic approach herein presented, LiFePO₄ is processed using lithium polyacrylic acid (Li-PAA) binder and water as the solvent, and its performance is compared to that of conventional electrodes processed using polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) binder and N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) toxic solvent. The aqueous-based electrode delivers superior long-term stability, retaining 83 % of its capacity after 800 cycles at 1 C. Our holistic and more sustainable approach, based on hydrothermal synthesis, biomass-derived carbon coating, and aqueous processing, delivers discharge capacities, charge transfer impedance, electrode diffusivity, and cycling performance comparable to that of less environmentally friendly methods and highlights the potential of replacing hazardous materials and processes with greener alternatives without compromising electrode properties and overall performance.

1. Introduction

Since the discovery of the electrochemical properties of LiFePO₄ (LFP) as a cathode for Li-ion batteries (LIBs) in 1996 by Goodenough and co-workers [1,2], the material performance has been thoroughly optimized, and nowadays, LFP is widely used in the battery industry, especially by manufacturers from Asia. LFP is appealing because it contains non-contaminant elements such as iron and phosphates and demonstrates good safety and electrochemical characteristics, including superior thermal and chemical stability compared to other cathode materials such as LiCoO₂, (Ni_{0.45}Mn_{0.45}Co_{0.10})O₂, or LiMn₂O₄, [3–7] as well as enhanced stability against electrolyte solutions at room

temperature [6,8]. At elevated temperatures in acidic electrolytes, it degrades through iron dissolution or resistive interface formation, avoiding harmful gas emissions [4,6,9]. Beyond its safety features, LFP boasts commendable electrochemical properties, including structural stability and a theoretical capacity of 170 mAh/g.

LFP presents an orthorhombic crystal structure with a *Pnma* space group. It is composed of PO₄ tetrahedra and two different octahedral sites: M1 (4a) occupied by Li, and M2 (4c) occupied by Fe, both coordinated with six oxygen atoms [1,10]. The FeO₆ octahedra are isolated, while LiO₆ groups are arranged to form one-dimensional channels in the [010] direction, allowing Li ion diffusion through the crystal. The strong covalent bonds in the LFP structure provide good stability but also

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hinder electron and ionic conductivity, which are the two principal challenges this material faces and the main drivers for the ongoing research for its improvement [11,12].

LFP's material properties and, therefore, its electrochemical behaviour, are strongly affected by the synthesis method and the experimental conditions used in its preparation. For instance, choosing the adequate synthesis parameters can yield smaller particle sizes or particle morphologies with short [010] channels which present shorter Li diffusion paths that favour Li mobility and lead to improved performance [13–16]. Literature also shows that low temperature wet syntheses [17–20] or high temperature treatments [21] can lead to position exchange of Li and Fe cations (antisite defects) while sample re-annealing can partially recover the ordered distribution of cations in the olivine structure [21]. The Fe atoms in these antisite defects block the Li diffusion channels and results in a decrease in the electrochemical properties of the material [17,22,23]. It has been consistently proven then, that the method and conditions (i.e. temperature, time, solvent type, type and concentration of the precursors) used in LFP synthesis have a critical effect on its structure (i.e. particle size, morphology, crystallinity, purity) and electrochemical properties. Various techniques can be used to synthesize LFP, being hydro/solvothermal [17–19,24,25], solid-state [21,26–28], sol-gel [29–34] and co-precipitation [29–32] the most frequently used, each with their own advantages and disadvantages [33–35].

In addition to the synthesis methodology and conditions, the use of dopants and powder coating are also common approaches to enhance LFP's overall performance [15,36–38]. The most practical and relatively straightforward approach is adding a carbon coating to increase electron conductivity, surface area, heat resistance, structural integrity, and compatibility with the materials used in battery cell assembly. The coating thickness must find a precise balance, being thick enough to facilitate good electron mobility while avoiding hindrance to the diffusion of lithium ions from the electrode to the electrolyte [36,37]. Among all the carbon precursors available for coating, biomass is a good option as it is widely available in nature, it is renewable, and its use is environmentally friendly, especially when derived from agricultural or forestry residues. In this sense, biomass-derived carbon coatings from orange [28] or potato peels [39] have already been applied to LFP with promising electrochemical results. Different carbon types can be obtained depending on the biomass origin, composition, and treatment, allowing for tailored adjustments to suit specific application requirements [40].

Besides the properties of active material, the composition and fabrication procedure of the cathode electrode are key factors that affect both the performance and sustainability of the battery. During electrode processing, the binder is pivotal in interconnecting electrochemically active and conductive particles, ensuring uniform adhesion of the active material to the current collector. Achieving uniformity and local aggregation is crucial for regulating the electrical and mechanical behaviour of the electrode. Traditionally, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), a widely used commercial binder, is recognized for its high chemical resistance, thermal stability, and electrochemical stability [41,42]. However, PVDF binders necessitate organic solvents, such as the frequently used N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), as a dispersion medium, which poses concerns related to high toxicity, volatility, and flammability. Additional challenges arise from PVDF decomposing in nitrogen atmosphere, producing highly toxic compounds, as well as swelling and dissolution in nonaqueous liquid electrolytes, leading to issues such as exfoliation of electrode particles, thereby compromising cycle stability and exacerbating capacity fading [41]. Furthermore, PVDF presents significant challenges in its separation from electrode active materials during recycling, often requiring extensive thermal and chemical processing [43]. Alternatively, several potential aqueous binders have been considered for the fabrication of LIB electrodes, including carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), sodium alginate (Na-Alg), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyacrylic acid (PAA), cellulose sulphate

lithium (CSL), and poly (3,4-ethylene dioxithiophene):poly (styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) among others [42,44]. The performance reaches 144 mAh/g at C/10 for LFP combined with PEDOT:PSS binder [43], 133.4 mAh/g at a high rate of 1 C with cellulose sulphate lithium (CSL) [45] and 134.4 mAh/g at 0.2 mA/g using Li-PAA as binder [46]. Their cost-effectiveness (e.g. 1–2 €/kg for Li-PAA) compared to organic solvent-based binders (e.g. PVDF 15–18 €/kg), together with the use of safer and less polluting solvents for the processing, underscore the attractiveness of water-based binders.

In this study, we have prepared an LFP cathode for LIBs using a more sustainable and holistic approach, from material synthesis to electrode processing, prioritizing environmentally friendly precursors and processes without compromising electrochemical performance. To achieve this, a defect-free LFP ceramic is prepared via hydrothermal synthesis using water as the reaction medium, and the resulting active particles are carbon-coated at 800 °C in an inert atmosphere using a biomass extract from vine leaves as carbon precursor. Additionally, we have replaced the traditional processing of electrodes, which uses a toxic solvent, with a more sustainable one, considering water and Li-PAA as solvent and binder, respectively. Two additional samples were prepared for comparison: one with sucrose as the carbon-coating precursor and another without any carbon coating.

Hydrothermal synthesis was selected as it yields high-performant LFP [17–19,24,25] while utilizing water as the reaction medium, eliminating the need for organic solvents, which are often less environmentally friendly. The process generates no harmful contaminants, unreacted raw materials can be recovered and reused in subsequent synthesis cycles, and the synthesis is conducted at relatively mild temperatures (typically ranging from 170 °C to 220 °C), enhancing its sustainability. To produce optimized materials, we assured a good selection of the precursors, the specific synthesis strategy (e.g., precursor addition order, use of additives), and the reaction conditions (temperature and duration), as all those factors determine the morphology (particle size and shape) and the properties of the final material. Post-treatment at high temperature is essential for optimizing LFP's electrochemical performance as it enhances crystallinity, resulting in a more ordered and stable structure with fewer antisite defects, and enables the application of the electron-conductive carbon coating.

Sucrose is commonly used as a carbon precursor for coating LFP particles. However, the use of sucrose for non-edible purposes is increasingly discouraged, as it directly competes with the global food supply [47–50]. In addition, certain methods of sucrose production, such as those based on sugarcane, are associated with environmental issues including soil erosion, biodiversity loss, excessive water use, and pollution from agricultural runoff and mill effluents [50,51]. On the contrary, second-generation biomass, consisting of agricultural residues that are typically discarded and may contribute to landfill accumulation and pollution, can be valorised, supporting the development of a circular economy [47,48,50,51]. Waste vine leaves have been selected to obtain the biomass extract used as a carbon precursor as it is one of the most abundant agrifood residues in the Mediterranean [52]. Both sucrose extraction from feedstocks and biomass extract preparation from vine leaves involve several common steps: washing the feedstock, extraction (using either physical or solvent-based methods), evaporation, centrifugation, and drying. Therefore, the carbon footprints of these extraction processes are expected to be broadly comparable, although this depends on factors such as the scale of operation, energy sources, and solvent usage.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Synthesis of LFP

The reagents used for the hydrothermal synthesis of LiFePO₄ were LiOH anhydrous (Sigma-Aldrich, 98 %), FeSO₄·7 H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, 98 %), and H₃PO₄ (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥ 85 wt% aqueous solution). The

mass of precursors was calculated to theoretically produce 0.01 mol of LFP using a Li:Fe:P molar ratio of 3:1:1. The LiOH was initially dissolved in 30 mL of water in a beaker, and the H_3PO_4 solution was added dropwise, forming a white precipitate. Then, ground $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added to the mixture, giving a greenish precipitate. The mixture was transferred into a 250 mL Teflon-lined autoclave using 20 mL of MilliQ water, and N_2 was bubbled into the mixture for 10 min. The autoclave was then introduced in an oven at 190 °C for 5 h. Afterwards, the obtained solid powder was washed 3 times with ethanol and 3 times with water using the centrifuge to separate the solids from the liquids. The slurry obtained was dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C and ground with a mortar to obtain a greenish-grey solid (sample label HT-LFP). Finally, the dry LFP was crystallized in a tubular oven at 600 °C for 12 h under Ar/H_2 gas flow, using a heating rate of 10 °C/min and with a previous purging step of 2 h at 100 °C under Ar/H_2 (sample label Pristine-LFP).

Previously, a biomass ethanolic extract was obtained from vine leaves in ethanol absolute (Sigma Aldrich) in a ratio wt:wt 1:6, the mixture was decanted. The obtained solution was stirred for 1 h while drops of hydrochloric acid (Sigma Aldrich, 37 %) were added until pH 1. The solution was concentrated and 50 mL of MilliQ water and 5 mL of ethyl ether (Sigma Aldrich, 99 %) were added to the mixture. The precipitate obtained was collected by centrifuging it at 8500 rpm for 6 min and then dried overnight at 85 °C.

The LFP was carbon coated using either sucrose (Sigma Aldrich, 99.5 %) or the biomass extract. For the C-coating with biomass (sample label LFP-Bi), 0.35 g of LFP active material was introduced in a flask with 0.2 g of biomass and 5 g of ethanol. Then, CH_2Cl_2 was added dropwise while vigorously stirring until we obtained an emulsion. The solvents were removed in a vacuum oven at 60 °C obtaining a brown powder, which was then pyrolyzed in a tubular oven at 800 °C for 2 h under N_2 flow. A heating rate of 5 °C/min and a gas pre-purging at 40 °C during 1 h under Ar flow (purity grade 5.0) were used. For the sucrose coating (sample label LFP-Su), 0.35 g of LFP was added in a flask with 0.1 g of sucrose and 5 g of MilliQ water. The mixture was agitated and sonicated for 20 min for a complete dissolution of the sucrose and a good mixing of the components. The water was then removed in an oven set at 80 °C, the obtained powder ground with a mortar, and pyrolyzed in a tubular oven at 800 °C for 2 h under N_2 flow. A heating rate of 5 °C/min and a previous gas purging at 40 °C during 1 h under Ar flow were used.

Three samples are mainly considered in this manuscript: LFP-Bi and LFP-Su, corresponding to carbon-coated LFP samples using biomass or sucrose, respectively, and an uncoated LFP sample thermally treated at the same conditions as the carbon-coated ones (800 °C and N_2 flow) and labelled LFP-NoC. Two extra samples labelled Pristine-LFP and HT-LFP were also considered for FTIR data analysis. Pristine-LFP corresponds to LFP prepared hydrothermally with crystallization at 600 °C, and HT-LFP refers to LFP prepared hydrothermally with no crystallization step.

2.2. Electrode and cell preparation

The electrochemical performance of LFPs was systematically investigated employing half-cells (vs Li metal). The working electrode was fabricated using 85.2 wt% LFP as the active material, 9.8 wt% Super P carbon from Alfa Aesar as the conducting agent, and 5 wt% of PVDF from MTI as binder. This mixture was prepared under an Ar atmosphere, using NMP as a solvent, and ball milled for 20 min at 20 Hz, using stainless steel balls with a ball-to-powder mass ratio of 26.7:1. The homogenized slurry obtained was uniformly applied by doctor blade to an aluminium film of 15 μm thickness as the substrate (current collector). Subsequently, it underwent a two-step drying process, initially at 90 °C for at least 10 min, followed by a second stage at 110 °C under vacuum conditions overnight. Finally, disk electrodes of 12 mm diameter with a loading of 2 mg/cm^2 were cut and stored inside the glove box. In the case of the aqueous processing, the same procedure was applied, with the only difference being the substitution of the binder and the solvent to Li-PAA and water, respectively, and the extended drying process in air

(≥ 1 h). A slower drying process is necessary as water has a lower boiling point than NMP, which, combined with the low viscosity of Li-PAA, may result in particle agglomeration if not controlled carefully. The assembly of 2032-type coin cells was carried out in an argon-filled glove box, employing a glass microfiber filter (Whatman GF/A) with a diameter of 16 mm as the separator. The electrolyte used was 1 M lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6) in ethylene carbonate (EC)/diethyl carbonate (DEC) (1:1, v/v; Sigma Aldrich) and metallic lithium foil was employed as the counter electrode. An electrolyte volume of 52.5 μl was used to wet each coin cell.

2.3. Characterization

The phase analysis of the synthesized powders was done by X-ray diffraction (XRD, D8 Advanced, Bruker). The XRD patterns were collected using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation within a 2θ range from 10° to 80°, with a step size of 0.005° and a total measuring time of 8:40 h. The Rietveld refinement of the crystal structure of LFP samples was performed with GSAS® software [53] using the least-squares minimization procedure. The background was fitted using a Chebyshev-1 function with a coefficient number of 6. The instrument's parameters U, V, W, X, and Y, corresponding to the Gaussian and Lorentzian components of the pseudo-Voigt peak shape function were also considered during the refinement until a good peak fit was obtained and then fixed. Structural models involved refining lattice parameters, atom coordinates, and Li and Fe occupancies. The structural model considered two constraints: antisite defect formation between 4a and 4c crystallographic positions, as previously reported for olivine-type materials, and a fixed anisotropic thermal displacement parameter for all atoms ($U_{iso} = 0.020 \text{ \AA}^2$).

The morphology of the obtained powders was studied with a Scanning electron microscope (ZEISS Auriga with a Gemini column) equipped with SE2 and In-Lens detectors. The morphology of the biomass and sucrose carbon coatings was analysed with a JEOL JEM2010 TEM 200 kV. The carbon content of the samples was quantified via combustion elemental analysis (EA 1112, Thermo Fisher Scientific). The structure of the carbon coatings was studied using Raman spectroscopy (Xplora Plus, Horiba France SAS). The acquisition was done with a 538 nm laser in the 500–2000 cm^{-1} range to observe the D and G bands. Infrared spectra of the samples were obtained with an Alpha FT-IR spectrometer (Bruker) equipped with an ATR (attenuated total reflection) accessory. The absorbance of the samples was measured in the range 375–4000 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra were baseline-corrected and normalized using Origin software for visual practical purposes.

Electrochemical tests were conducted by galvanostatic cycling in Neware CT-4008T test stations at 25 °C within a voltage range from 3 to 4 V, encompassing C-Rates of C/20, C/10, C/5 and C/2, while the voltage range was extended for 1 C and 2 C from 2.7 to 4 V. For each sample, at least three coin cells were prepared and analysed. From their results, average capacities and standard deviation were calculated. Cyclic voltammetry was executed at a scan rate of 0.333 mV/s from 3 to 4 V in the uncoated LFP and from 2.7 to 4 V for the coated LFP samples in Biologic BCS-805 and BCS-810 devices. Electrochemical impedance measurements (EIS) were conducted after CV measurements by applying an AC voltage of 10 mV amplitude in the frequency range of 10 kHz to 10 mHz in the discharge state. Preceding the tests, the battery underwent a relaxation period to attain its equilibrium potential of 24 h.

3. Results and discussion

The XRD diffractograms of LFP carbon-coated samples (LFP-Bi and LFP-Su) and bare LFP (LFP-NoC) are presented in Fig. 1a). XRD patterns show that LFP carbon-coated samples are phase pure. In contrast, the sample without carbon contains the oxide Fe_2O_3 and the phosphate $\text{Li}_3\text{Fe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ as impurities. LFP is extremely sensitive to oxidation, and even though the thermal treatment at 800 °C is performed under an inert atmosphere, a small fraction of it can react with the oxygen impurities

Fig. 1. XRD analysis: a) XRD diffractograms of the three samples with the reference LFP peaks marked as grey vertical lines and impurity peaks marked with asterisks (*) and minus signs (-), b) Table showing lattice parameters and unit cell volume for the three samples with some references. HT: hydrothermal synthesis, SSS: solid-state synthesis, CR: crystallization and CC: carbon coating.

(≤ 2 ppm) from the inert gas. In LFP-Bi and LFP-Su, the carbon precursors act as protective agents that prevent the oxidation of the iron. Diffraction patterns were indexed using an orthorhombic unit cell, and results are presented in Fig. 1b). The lattice parameters are very similar for the three samples, with an average unit cell volume of $293.16(1) \text{ \AA}^3$, since all samples were thermally treated to the same temperature of $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Using lattice parameters from peak indexing and structural model obtained from [21], LFP crystal structures were refined, and results for sample LFP-Bi are presented in Fig. 2. Results for LFP-Su and LFP-NoC are presented in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information. The structural models involved refining lattice parameters, atom coordinates, and Li and Fe occupancies. The profile plot showing the experimental, calculated, and difference profiles for LFP-Bi is shown in Fig. 2a). The evolution of goodness-of-fit indicators and the visual inspection of the profile plots indicated a satisfactory refinement for all three samples. Cation exchange is not observed for the three samples since refined occupancies (%) are close to 100. An ordered structure is confirmed for LFP independently of the presence or absence and type of carbon precursors. As previously discussed by some of us [21], the cation exchange phenomena in olivine materials can be understood as an equilibrium process favoured at higher calcination temperatures of $> 900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Infrared spectroscopy was used as a quick and complementary technique to evaluate antisite disorder in the samples. Qin et al. [18] reported that changes in the cation site positions affect the IR absorption band under 1000 cm^{-1} , assigned to the symmetric stretching of the P-O bond in the PO_4 tetrahedron. A lower content of antisite defects results in a band shift to lower wavenumbers. Fig. 3 shows the IR spectra of the three samples (LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, and LFP-NoC) and data for Pristine-LFP and HT-LFP, which correspond to LFP prepared hydrothermally at $190 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with or without annealing step at $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The HT-LFP sample is expected to have some antisite defects [17–19]. In contrast, sample annealing at relatively high temperatures of $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for Pristine-LFP and $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, and LFP-NoC should allow the reorganization of the Li and Fe atoms to their more stable positions [21]. These assumptions are consistent with the qualitative results in Fig. 3, showing a band shift from 980 to 963 and 957 cm^{-1} for the sample series. These findings prove that dry thermal treatment at temperatures $600\text{--}800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are successful in reducing the content of antisite defects and improving the material properties. They also show that this atom reorganization occurs independently of the presence and type of carbon coating and agree with the results in Fig. 2b and Figure S1 (Supporting information), which show similar and low cation exchange for the LFP-Bi, LFP-Su and LFP-NoC samples.

Fig. 2. LFP-Bi crystal structure and XRD refinement: a) Observed, calculated, and difference profiles of XRD data for LFP-Bi, b) crystal structure of the LFP-Bi with Li atoms represented as red spheres, oxygens as grey spheres, FeO_6 as turquoise octahedra and PO_4 as ochre tetrahedra, c) Structural parameters obtained from Rietveld refinement of LFP-Bi crystal structure.

Fig. 3. IR analysis: a) IR spectra of LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, LFP-NoC, HT-LFP obtained after hydrothermal liquefaction and Pristine-LFP obtained after crystallization at 600 °C. b) zoom-in to the P-O st. vibration band.

SEM images of the ceramic microstructure, particle size distribution and cumulative distribution at percentages 10, 50 and 90 % (D10, D50 and D90) for the three samples are presented in Fig. 4. SEM images show partially agglomerated spheric and ellipsoid particles, like those

reported by Alsamet et al. [54], who synthesized LFP under very similar conditions. The particle size distribution was determined by manually measuring the particles observed in the SEM images using ImageJ software [55]. For each material, a minimum of 100 particles was

Fig. 4. SEM and PSD analysis: SEM images, particle size distribution and cumulative distribution of the a-b) LFP-Bi, c-d) LFP-Su and e-f) LFP-NoC.

analysed to ensure representative results. The longest and shortest dimensions for every particle were measured and incorporated into the calculations. Minimal particle morphology and size changes are observed between LFP-Bi (a-b) and LFP-Su (c-d), which display a median diameter (D50) of 0.35–0.36 μm for the spheric particles. On the contrary, the LFP-NoC (e-f) shows significant changes, with a general particle growth but also the formation of a substantial number of small particles (< 200 nm) that most probably correspond to the impurity phases observed in the XRD spectrum, Fig. 1a). The SEM and particle size analyses confirm the protective nature of the carbon layer against particle oxidation, growth, and agglomeration.

According to elemental analysis, the two carbon-coated samples contain a similar amount of carbon: 3.15 wt% and 3.46 wt% for LFP-Bi and LFP-Su, respectively, due to the pyrolyzing process conducted in inert conditions. Raman spectroscopy was performed to investigate the carbon structure of LFP-Bi and LFP-Su, and the results are presented in Fig. 5a). Carbon black (Super P, Alfa Aesar) was also analysed for comparison as it is commonly used as a conductive additive in electrode processing. The characteristic D and G bands located at the Raman shifts of 1350 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} , respectively, are used to determine the disorder/graphitization degree of the carbon [56]. Fig. 5a) shows identical D and G band profiles for LFP-Bi and LFP-Su, with a D/G intensity ratio of 0.96 for both samples. This indicates that carbonization leads to a similar carbon structure independently of the carbon source (biomass or sucrose). The D/G Intensity ratio for the carbon Super P is similar ~ 1.03 , indicating that the three carbons have a similar disorder/graphitization ratio and an adequate carbon structure for electronic conduction. The band at 950 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the symmetric PO_4^{3-} stretching vibration of LiFePO_4 (Ag mode of ν_1), is observed in LFP-Bi and LFP-Su evidencing the preservation of crystallinity for both routes.

TEM images of LFP-Bi and LFP-Su and carbon coatings are shown in Fig. 5(b-g). LFP-Su presents a relatively homogeneous carbon coating with a thickness that ranges from 1 to 6 nm (Fig. 5b-d). This carbon layer seems to act as a binder between particles and is weakly attached to the LFP, as can be deduced from the presence of amorphous, light cloth-type structures. Krumeich et al. [57] observed similar behaviour for carbon-coated LFP samples annealed > 800 $^\circ\text{C}$. LFP-Bi (Fig. 5e-g) also presents a weakly attached carbon layer acting as a binder but this layer appears less homogeneous, being absent in some regions while reaching a thickness of up to 10 nm in others. The difference in the homogeneity of the carbon coating in the LFP-Su and LFP-Bi samples is possibly caused by the different structures of the carbon precursors. While sucrose consists of a homogeneous substrate composed of small molecules that can be dissolved in water and homogeneously deposited on the LFP surface, the biomass extract partially maintains the structure of the initial chloroplasts and, therefore, does not have a homogeneous size

and morphology [58].

Electrochemical tests of LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, and LFP-NoC electrodes were conducted in half-cells (vs. Li/Li+). Fig. 7e) shows the CV plots for the three samples. The redox peaks observed in the anodic and cathodic regions correspond to the $\text{Fe}^{3+/2+}$ redox couple, characteristic of the lithium intercalation/deintercalation process in LFP cathodes. The CVs of the biomass and sucrose samples show almost identical oxidation and reduction peak positions, indicating similar reversibility of the reactions for both samples. Additionally, the peak currents for both oxidation and reduction peaks are similar. The LFP-NoC presents an asymmetric CV with a larger peak-to-peak separation, indicating less reversibility and slower kinetics for the reaction. From the peak positions and shape, we can anticipate a larger charge-transfer resistance for the non-coated LFP sample [59], which is consistent with the absence of the electron-conductive carbon coating.

EIS was used to measure the different resistance components in discharged samples after CV measurements. Fig. 6a) shows the Nyquist plots for the three samples. The first Z' intercept at the highest frequencies is attributed to the electrolyte resistance, which encompasses both the internal resistance of the electrolyte and its ability to infiltrate the porous structure of the cathode material [60]. The high-frequency semicircle observed is due to the charge transfer resistance [61], which arises at the interface between the active material particles and the electrolyte. This resistance reflects the difficulty of electron transfer during the redox reactions at the electrode-electrolyte interface with values of 108.3 Ω and 70.45 Ω for LFP-Bi and LFP-Su respectively. The slightly lower resistance obtained for LFP-Su may be attributed to its more homogeneous coating compared to LFP-Bi. In contrast, the charge transfer resistance of LFP-NoC exceeds 1500 Ω , demonstrating the critical role of the conducting carbon coating in enhancing efficient electron transport. Finally, the sloping line in the low frequency at 45° region is related to the diffusion of lithium ions within the electrode material and is associated with the Warburg coefficient [60], which reflects the ionic diffusion limitations.

The equivalent circuit model and fitting parameters for the three samples were obtained with Bio-Logic EC Lab software using a Randomize-Simplex method, and the results are shown in Fig. 6c). In the model, the electrolyte resistance (R_e) corresponds to R_1 , and the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) can be obtained by subtracting R_1 from R_2 . Q_2 represents the non-ideal capacitance associated with the semicircle, as its behaviour deviates from that of an ideal capacitor. Additionally, a Q_3 element is needed to fit low-frequency data. The Nyquist plot of such an element corresponds to a straight line in the imaginary positive part $-Z_1$ with a value of $-\pi/2$ angle with the real axis. So, if the parameter a_3 is equal to or close to 0.5, the Warburg element can be associated with this constant phase element and, therefore, associated to the lithium diffusivity process within the electrode. The fitted parameter a_3 is 0.44 for

Fig. 5. Raman and TEM analysis: a) Raman spectra of biomass and sucrose carbons and TEM images of the b-d) LFP-Su and e-g) LFP-Bi.

Fig. 6. EIS analysis, equivalent circuit, fitting, and Warburg diagrams: a) Nyquist plots, b) Warburg diagrams, c) Equivalent circuit model, d) graphic fitting and e) Parameters and calculated values used to obtain Li diffusivities at the electrode level, for LFP-Bi, LFP-Su and LFP-NoC.

LFP-Bi, 0.6 for LFP-NoC, and 0.53 for LFP-Su.

To determine the Li diffusion coefficient in the LFP particles, a linear regression analysis was performed between the real part of the impedance (Z') and the reciprocal of the square root of the angular frequency ($\omega^{-0.5}$) in the low-frequency region (Fig. 6b). The Warburg coefficient (σ) is obtained from the slope of this fitted line, where ω represents the angular frequency in the low-frequency domain (Eq. 1). The Li diffusion coefficient (D_{Li}) is directly related to the Warburg coefficient (σ) and can be calculated using the Randles-Sevcik equation [62,63] (Eq. 2):

$$Z_r = \sigma \times \omega^{-0.5} + R_{ct} \quad (1)$$

$$D_{Li} = \frac{R^2 \times T^2}{2 \times A^2 \times n^4 \times F^4 \times C_{Li}^2 \times \sigma^2} \quad (2)$$

Where R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, A is the active surface area of the electrode, n is the number of electrons involved in the redox reaction per molecule, F is the Faraday constant, C_{Li} is the molar concentration of Li intercalated in the LFP electrode, and σ is the Warburg coefficient.

To calculate the molar concentration of Li, the following formula is assumed:

$$C_{Li} = \frac{\frac{m_{\text{activematerial}}}{Mm_{\text{LFP}}}}{A \times e} \quad (3)$$

Where m is the mass of the active material, Mm_{LFP} represents the molecular mass of LFP, and e denotes the thickness of the electrode assembled in the coin cell, excluding the aluminium substrate. This analysis assumes that the dynamic limitations from electrode resistance are negligible and doesn't consider the electrode's porosity.

Based on this method, the calculated Li diffusion coefficients are $5.67 \cdot 10^{-11}$, $5.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$, and $8.25 \cdot 10^{-14}$ cm^2/s for LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, and

LFP-NoC, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6e). The similar results obtained for LFP-Bi and LFP-Su are coherent with the fact that both samples present very similar crystal structure and morphology, and the diffusivity values are inside the range reported for LFP [64,65]. In contrast, the LFP-NoC presents a considerably lower Li diffusion, which could be caused by the longer path the Li ions must travel to exit the LFP particle due to its bigger particle size and the impurities detected in the XRD measurements.

Fig. 7a) and c) shows the galvanostatic cycling results of the LFP-Bi compared with the LFP-Su and the uncoated LFP-NoC at various C-rates

Fig. 7. Galvanostatic cycling, durability tests and CV analysis: a) Galvanostatic cycling at various C-rates for LFP-Bi, LFP-Su and LFP-NoC, b) Galvanostatic cycling at various C-rates for LFP-Bi electrode processed using NMP and electrode processed using water, c) Durability test performed at 1C during 100 cycles for coated LFP-Bi and LFP-Su samples, d) Durability tests performed at 1C during 800 cycles for LFP-Bi processed using NMP and processed using water, e) CV for LFP-Bi, LFP-Su, and LFP-NoC and f) CV of LFP-Bi using Li-PAA in water and PVDF in NMP.

and the durability tests at 1 C of the coated LFP samples. LFP-Bi and LFP-Su exhibit similar discharge capacities at the various tested rates, delivering 109.61 mAh/g and 106.28 mAh/g at C/5 respectively. As expected, capacity decreases with increasing C-rate but recovers and even increases when returning to lower C-rates. This increment at low C rates can be explained because initial cycles at C/20 and C/10 belong to the formation of the passivation layer, so once the electrode is activated, it delivers its optimal capacity. Unsurprisingly, LFP-NoC shows a considerably lower capacity than the coated materials at low C-rates, delivering 15.25 mAh/g at C/5 and decreasing to zero at C/2 rates and higher. These results confirm the importance of carbon-coating on the LFP performance since bare LFP is an insulating material. In terms of durability, Fig. 7c), both LFP-Bi and LFP-Su show good stability with a capacity retention of 98 % and 96 %, respectively, after more than 100 cycles at 1 C.

Continuing with the holistic approach to enhancing LFP sustainability, a more environmentally friendly method for electrode processing using Li-PAA and water as binder and solvent was evaluated using the LFP-Bi sample. The electrode morphology is presented in Figure S3 a-d), and the electrode CV response using a scan rate of 0.333 mV/s is presented in Fig. 7f). SEM micrographs display a homogeneous coating for the aqueous processing (Figure S3 a-b), indicating that the manufacturing process is well-controlled, as in the case of NMP processing (Figure S3 c-d). The CVs of both samples suggest better charge transfer characteristics for the water-based electrode (Fig. 7f), which displays a shorter peak-to-peak separation of 0.24 V and a steeper increase at the beginning of the oxidation and reduction peaks compared to the 0.56 V peak-to-peak gap and rounder peak shape in NMP-based electrode. These results agree with those reported by Cai et al. [46] who observed the similar CV profiles and attributed them to a better reversibility resulting from lower solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) resistance on the LFP surface and enhanced charge transfer during lithium-ion intercalation and deintercalation. However, water-based sample also shows less symmetry in its peaks, with a lower reduction peak area that indicates lower capacity during the discharge process.

Galvanostatic charge/discharge tests were conducted to compare the performance of water- and NMP-based electrodes (Fig. 7b) and d). Regarding discharge capacity, both electrodes deliver a similar performance of $\sim 100 \text{ mAhg}^{-1}$ at C/5, considering the averaged cell results and their standard deviations for cycles 25–30 (Fig. 7b). The electrode processed using water and Li-PAA binder needs a significantly longer activation than the NMP-based electrode. This is also observed by the durability test results for both electrodes, which are presented in Fig. 7d). The tests were conducted at 1 C for 800 cycles. The water-based electrode delivers a discharge capacity of 73.21 mAhg⁻¹ after 800 cycles, corresponding to a capacity retention of 83.36 %. The NMP-based electrode delivers a discharge capacity of 70.33 mAhg⁻¹ after 800 cycles with a capacity retention of 72.84 %. The charge-discharge coulombic efficiency is also improved for the Li-PAA processing, Table 1, from 87.65 % to 97.10 %. Cai et al. also reported better stability for water-based than for NMP-based electrodes [46], and Pieczonka et al. [66] conducted experiments using Li-PAA binder for LNMO processing and concluded that this binder acts as a protective layer covering the active particles while ensuring a stable particle-electrolyte interphase leading to an enhanced long-term performance.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates a holistic approach to improving the sustainability of LiFePO₄ cathodes, from material synthesis and processing to electrode fabrication. LiFePO₄ delivers robust cycle life and safety performance at a low cost, so it is becoming the material of choice for emerging European battery manufacturing companies. In this new scenario, it is important to consider new precursor materials and fabrication processes that do not compromise the balance between growth and environmental care. Following this principle, we have implemented

Table 1

Charge-discharge efficiencies and capacity retention for LFP-Bi electrodes processed using NMP and water, at 1 C.

Material	Chg-DChg Eff (%) average	Capacity retention (%) after 300 cycles	Capacity retention (%) after 800 cycles
LFP-Bi NMP based	87.65	79.69	72.84
LFP-Bi Water based	97.10	88.78	83.36

three actions for LFP synthesis and processing to reduce the cathode's environmental impact. First, synthesis is conducted via hydrothermal synthesis using salts, and secondly, the carbon-coating process uses biomass waste from vine leaves as carbon precursor. The biomass-derived carbon-coated LFP sample is phase-pure with an ordered distribution of Li and Fe cations in the unit cell, as evaluated by Rietveld refinement of the crystal structure; this is supported by FTIR qualitative analyses using samples with different degrees of cation ordering. The carbon coating for electronic conduction has been validated by Raman spectroscopy and TEM imaging, and its structure is very similar to the one obtained using sucrose as a carbon precursor. The carbon-coating process is essential to ensure phase purity, homogenous particle distribution, and high conductivity for the electrode transfer between active particles and the current collector. EIS data demonstrates a low charge transfer resistance and high lithium diffusivity compared to an uncoated sample, in the order of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ S/cm}^2$, as expected for LFP cathodes. This results in a discharge capacity of 96 mAh/g at 1 C and capacity retention of 98 % after 100 cycles, comparable to carbon-coated LFP using sucrose. The more sustainable LFP sample obtained from greener synthesis and carbon coating using biomass was considered for aqueous electrode processing with Li-PAA. The greener electrode delivers superior long-term stability, retaining 83 % of its capacity after 800 cycles at 1 C compared to 72 % for standard NMP processing. This demonstrates the feasibility of preparing LFP cathodes from a holistic and sustainable approach without compromising performance.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nxmate.2025.101312](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nxmate.2025.101312).

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